

PAIR

Pandemic Information
to Support Rapid Response

The logo consists of a blue graphic element on the left, which is a stylized gear or cogwheel with a semi-circular shape on its right side. To the right of this graphic, the word "PAIR" is written in a bold, blue, sans-serif typeface.

BRANDMARK - VARIATIONS

NEGATIVE - COLORED

NEGATIVE - BLACK AND WHITE

NEGATIVE - BLACK AND WHITE

BRANDMARK - SAFE AREA

COLOR PALETTE

C 0
M 0
Y 0
K 0

R 255
G 255
B 255
#FFFFFF

C 11
M 7
Y 9
K 0

R 232
G 232
B 232
#E8E8E8

C 90
M 70
Y 2
K 0

R 33
G 86
B 162
#2156A2

C 0
M 93
Y 33
K 0

R 237
G 35
B 103
#ED2367

C 73
M 63
Y 59
K 75

R 38
G 38
B 38
#262626

TYPOGRAPHY - FONT

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET CONSECTETUR

Pandemic Information to Support Rapid Response

SUBTITLES: **ACUMIN PRO BOLD**

TITLES: **ACUMIN PRO REGULAR**

Linking rapid, reliable testing with comprehensive modelling
of potential impacts.

PARAGRAPHS: **ACUMIN PRO REGULAR**

The platform is based on a pathogen genomic drifting model to predict the risk of animal
pathogens drifting to become human pathogens
and an epidemiological model to predict geographical and temporal outbreaks of zoonoses.

TYPOGRAPHY - FALLBACK FONT

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET CONSECTETUR

Pandemic Information to Support Rapid Response

SUBTITLES: **ARIAL BOLD**

TITLES: **ARIAL REGULAR**

Linking rapid, reliable testing with comprehensive modelling
of potential impacts.

PARAGRAPHS: **ARIAL REGULAR**

The platform is based on a pathogen genomic drifting model to predict the risk of animal
pathogens drifting to become human pathogens
and an epidemiological model to predict geographical and temporal outbreaks of zoonoses.

ICONOGRAPHY - PHOTOGRAPHY EXAMPLES

HUMAN SAMPLE

ANIMAL SAMPLE

ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLE